

**IMPLEMENTATION OF ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN
TEACHING CHEMISTRY LESSONS**

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Annotation: *In this article, the effectiveness of the use of innovative technologies in chemistry education, the fact that in the teaching of chemistry, students are focused on independent work, the ability to apply chemical knowledge in the interpretation of surrounding phenomena, especially in groups, and the performance of independent tasks leads to good results. opinions are expressed.*

Keywords: *combination lesson;-chain lesson;-computer lesson;- "Zig-zag" strategy;- "Stop-stop" reading strategy;- "Insert" strategy;- "Cubic" strategy, excursions.*

The positive changes taking place in our republic mean that there will be certain innovations and fundamental changes in the field of education. In fact, the issue of raising a well-educated, well-rounded person requires pedagogues to implement new work principles and imposes a great responsibility. One of the tasks of a modern teacher should be to create conditions for students to work independently, to make them interested in the subject, to make a deep understanding of the events that happen in life with the help of the knowledge acquired at school. [4]

In the teaching of chemistry, we should direct students to work independently, to be able to apply chemical knowledge in the interpretation of the surrounding phenomena. In the teaching of chemistry, especially in groups, doing independent tasks leads to good results. Students think independently, try to work creatively, even low-educated students strive to be among the "good students", and this situation raises the group's performance.

In the process of performing various individual, group, and independent work in pairs, students' knowledge deepens, skills are formed

- this is appropriate. Independent work with the book should be done more, we will start using additional literature, let them make crosswords, quizzes. It is even better if we organize extracurricular activities, excursions, parties, because chemistry is a science of life, and if its students master chemical knowledge, no matter what field they will occupy in the future, we can say that they are mature people.

Appearances of chemistry classes based on advanced pedagogical technologies will be different. A common feature of the lessons is the creative approach of the teacher.

Chemistry lessons can be:

- the lesson of imparting new knowledge to students;
 - lessons of generalization and systematization of knowledge;
 - repetition, strengthening, formation of qualifications and skills;
 - knowledge control;
 - combination lesson;
 - repetition, strengthening, formation of qualifications and skills;
 - knowledge control;
 - combination lesson;
 - research lesson;
 - research lesson;
 - a lesson on working with an independent textbook;
 - discussion class;
 - game lesson;
 - seminar and lecture classes;
 - the lesson of intersubject communication;
 - cooperative lesson;
 - chain lesson;-
 - free thinker class;
 - the lesson of practical training;-
 - computer class;
 - one person for all, all for one person;
- In addition to these, there are also teaching methods:
- free writing;
 - analysis of sexematic features; - asking each other;
 - "Zig-zag" strategy;
 - "Stop-stop" reading strategy;
 - "Insert" strategy;
 - "Cubic" strategy.

Such lessons awaken in students the desire to study and acquire knowledge, develop their independent creative research, independently and freely.

strengthens their thinking.

The most important thing is that the lesson develops the student education. Such a lesson can be considered a modern lesson.

All students actively participate in modern classes. The students themselves lead and study the lesson. The teacher acts as a participant and manager of the lesson process. The results of the lesson are evaluated by the students themselves. The teacher acts as a supervisor and manager.

The effectiveness of the lesson depends on its clear and clear organization. 70% of the time allocated for the lesson should be occupied by the student and 30% by the teacher. Based on this, in the course of the lesson, it is clearly indicated which elements of it are performed by the teacher and which elements are performed by the students themselves.[5]

There are specific aspects of using advanced pedagogical technologies in teaching chemistry:

a) Methodological aspects:

- taking into account the age characteristics of students;
- level of knowledge of students;
- students' interests;
- Suitability of the studied material to the student;
- scientificity of the studied materials;
- modernity and historicity of the material;
- the vitality of the studied material.

b) Lesson based on experiment:

- start the lesson based on problem experience;
- experimental lesson;
- problem, laboratory, observation lessons.

c) Control lesson:

- control and evaluation of students' knowledge;
- use of the basic outline;
- use of additional literature;
- from algorithmic methods in the process of teaching based on generalization tables use;

- analysis of the results obtained from the observation;

In such classes, the teacher: combines education and upbringing, independent knowledge

organizes acquisition, develops creative abilities.

A freely organized creative lesson is interesting for the student and brings him joy. The teacher unexpectedly asks the student questions. These questions are not only related to chemistry, but also related to literature, sports, music, technology, environment, and nature.

For this, it is necessary to educate the following: ingenuity, speed of understanding: mental sharpness, ability to quickly acquire knowledge, quick understanding of the problem, memorization, memory. As a result, students feel free and independent.

Creative cooperation is formed between teachers and students. The student strives to gain independent knowledge and begins to realize his activity as a higher form.

A systematic approach to education, relying on various pedagogical technologies to prepare students for creative work, to guide them to knowledge and practical activities, to save learning time, make the lesson interesting and make the student Achieving high efficiency as a result of not being tired shows the result of a creative lesson.

When organizing a lesson, it is necessary to consider the student not as an object of influence, but as a partner participating in the creative process. The result of the lesson is effective

it is necessary to involve students in various activities: freely and quickly thinking, understanding problems with dexterity, solving problems quickly

search for ways and come to a clear conclusion. This process is for students

develops creative abilities.

In the process of education, students are encouraged to learn independently

putting, developing creative abilities, free thinking, in interactions such as teaching active participation, increasing their interest in studying

types of educational activities form the basis of advanced pedagogical technology.

Independent educational activity is an activity that does not require any external influence and requires a creative approach. Any skill in this field

it is formed and developed only in the process of human activity. This point is important in the implementation of chemistry teaching. Because chemistry is studied on the basis of experimental facts, theoretical

conclusions are drawn from it, aspects that can be used in practice are considered.

Advanced pedagogical technologies, which require the development of students' creative abilities, in turn require the modernization of the content of chemical education, that is, the coordination of the course with the level of scientific progress and modern achievements of science and technology.

Therefore, advanced pedagogical technologies made it possible to increase the scientific content of chemistry education.[6]

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